

2nd GHRSSST Short Course on

Sea Surface Temperature

31 May—2 June 2017, OUC, Qingdao, China

Objectives

The GHRSSST short course on SST aims to:

- Gain knowledge about GHRSSST and what GHRSSST provides
- Gain knowledge of IR radiative transfer, cloud masking and SST retrieval
- Apply the gained knowledge with real practical examples

The course will include formal lectures as well as hands-on computing exercises using GHRSSST data.

Lecturers

Chris Merchant (University of Reading, UK) Gary Corlett (University of Leicester, UK)
Peter Minnett (University of Miami, USA) Mingqiang Fang (Ocean University of China)

Participation

Post graduate, PhD students, post doctoral research scientists or other users from China interested in Ocean Remote Sensing are invited to apply to the 3 day course.

Applications

The number of participants is limited to a maximum of 20 students and subject to selection of application. To apply, please complete the provided application form, and email it to Dr Gary Corlett (UoL, gpc@ghrsst.org) and Prof Lei Guan (OUC, leiguan@ouc.edu.cn) no later than Monday 22nd May 2017.

Venue

Ocean University of China, Qingdao, China